

AN ARTISTIC INTERPRETATION OF A HISTORICAL FIGURE'S CHARACTER

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Annotation: *This article explores the artistic interpretation of a real historical figure – Alisher Navoi – in modern Uzbek literature. Special attention is given to Omon Muxtor's novel “Ishq ahli”, analyzing the stylistic approaches to constructing Navoi's image, the spiritual and aesthetic reflections, and the psychological harmony between the author and the protagonist. The unique genre features of the novel are also examined.*

Keywords: *Alisher Navoi, artistic interpretation, historical figure, novel, essay, psychology of creativity, modern Uzbek prose, associativity, compositional style, author-character relationship.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается художественная интерпретация реальной исторической личности — Алишера Навои — в современной узбекской литературе. Особое внимание уделено роману Омон Мухтора «Ишқ аҳли», анализируются стилевые приёмы построения образа Навои, духовно-эстетические отражения и психологическая гармония между автором и главным героем. Также изучаются уникальные жанровые особенности романа.*

Ключевые слова: *Алишер Навои, художественная интерпретация, историческая личность, роман, эссе, психология творчества, современная узбекская проза, ассоциативность, композиционный стиль, взаимоотношения автора и героя.*

In our literary studies, the analysis of artistic interpretation principles regarding the character of real historical figures—particularly the depiction of Alisher Navoi in modern novels—has received relatively little scholarly attention. Yet, the artistic portrayal of a genius such as Alisher Navoi occupies a significant layer in both oral and written literature. From this perspective, this article analyzes *Ishq ahli*, a novel by Omon Muxtor, which emerged in the context of transformations and innovations characterizing the literary process of the second millennium.

Academic M. Qoshjonov, commenting on *Ishq ahli*, noted: “This new novel can be considered a major and matured stylistic achievement by the author. Omon Muxtor's work dedicated to Navoi is not merely a unique artistic experiment within Navoi studies and Navoi scholarship, but also a notable innovation in the development of Uzbek literature.” [Qo'shjonov, 2001.15] According to literary scholar Z. Pardayeva, the genre of this novel is defined as an essay based on the synthesis of artistic and scholarly elements in the author's analysis [Pardayeva, 2002. 45]. Hence, both academic M. Qoshjonov and Professor Z. Pardayeva emphasized

that the work is devoted to revealing the psychological aspects of Navoi’s creative world.

Observations show that associative techniques are strongly expressed in the narrative structure of the novel. In terms of architectonics, a compositional modeling method has been actively employed. This is no coincidence, as it relates to the nature of the essay genre itself—fluid, capable of synthesizing other forms of art, and possessing what Mikhail Bakhtin called a “well-kneaded form.” In modern prose, the construction of the plot is no longer restricted by strict rules; instead, the dynamic flow of events and the artist’s ability to extract their essence is prioritized. External factors—such as the chronological sequencing of the story or spatial changes of events, and the gradual presentation of characters with consistent logical argumentation—are considered less essential. The growing prominence of subjective elements intensifies the focus on the inner world of the individual, their thoughts and reflections, shifting the attention toward the dialectics of the soul. In this context, traditional principles of situating life events in a causally sequential timeline are replaced by episodes revived in the author's memory. In other words, epic events are enriched through internal emotional processes.

Of course, this phenomenon did not emerge all at once. If we pay attention, Oybek had already strived to depict the psychology of the poet’s creativity in his epic poem Navoi. He focused on the great poet’s thoughts and reflections. In *Guli va Navoiy*, he leaned on folk legends. Similarly, in the drama *Alisher Navoi* by Uyg‘un and I. Sulton, many of the attributes associated with Navoi’s image were drawn from his works and oral folk creativity. Such artistic explorations created a unity between the perspectives of the protagonist and the authors. All of these features are also characteristic of Omon Muxtor’s novel *Ishq ahli*. For example, in *Tepalikdagi xaroba*, Muxtor revives the images of historical figures such as Lutfi, Mashrab, Byron, Mirzo Ghalib, Amir Temur, Babur, and Akbar; in *Ayollar mamlakati va saltanati*, he presents Nodirabegim; and in *Aflotun*, he portrays Bahouddin Naqshband, Fayzulla Khojayev, Abdurauf Fitrat, and Ismail Samani. Through these works, he expresses a yearning for virtuous individuals, a spiritual connection with ancestors, and an aspiration to be a worthy heir to the sorrows and longings symbolized by the idea of “*Turkiston qayg‘usi*” (Turkestan’s grief).

The prose writer, whose veins carry the blood of ancestors and who seeks healing for the pains of the age, clearly draws inspiration from the courage and conviction of those forebears—truly going, as Fitrat once said, “to take kohl from the soil of his forefathers.” Thus, O. Muxtor’s inner world, his creative concept, and his

formal-stylistic pursuits are interconnected by a solid inner logic. Creating works in this style is not his first step, but rather a well-tested path. When defining his holistic stylistic orientation, it is essential to consider his perception of reality, the techniques he employs in artistic expression, his unique authorial position, and his writing manner. Only then do the recurring features from one work to another and the ever-evolving hallmarks of his style become more clearly visible.

In *Ishq ahli*, the details surrounding the notebooks of Abulkhayr, sent to Barno by Odil, form a unique framing narrative. Barno is a thoughtful, composed, and modest young woman. At the same time, she serves as a means to address every reader who shares these traits. She acts as a bridge for living dialogue between the author and the reader. Barno's character symbolizes a love that is rediscovered anew each day through the writer's imagination. Her strength in overcoming hardships lies in the refuge of the love she carries within—a sign of spiritual kinship with noble souls. Over the years, she has searched, explored, transformed, and sought self-understanding, and in doing so, has received guidance along the way. It becomes clear that the notebooks attributed to Abulkhayr in the novel are in fact derived from O. Muxtor's own reflections. The desire to “gather these messy notes into one volume and place them in a proper spot” stems from a yearning to shield oneself from negligence. Odil's words to Barno (and indirectly to the reader on behalf of the author) reinforce this: “... it's not quite right to compare the notes in this notebook to works by writers or books by scholars. It's better to consider them as the observations of a single person, an artist... He didn't write these as debates. On the contrary, he made use of the writings of others (referring to Oybek, I. Sulton, Uyg'un, T. Fayziy, H. Vambery, L. Bat)... In addition, he examined Arabic and Persian manuscripts.”

To understand Barno, or more precisely, to feel her, one must consider two specific emotional episodes in the novel associated with Abulkhayr's inner world, as Odil says: “...I've been keeping them hidden from everyone. I think she's the kind of person who reflects deeply.”

The First Episode. In the opening lines of the first notebook, it is written: “When I was a child, my grandmother would sit beside me on a bench and read Mir Alisher's ghazals aloud, telling me wondrous tales. Since then, I've longed to see the figure of the great man. I search. But will anything ever come of it? I don't know. I'm nearing the age of sixty. It's the length of the poet's entire life! I feel like an ant at the foot of a mountain.”

The Second Episode. At the end of the novel, in the fifth notebook, it reads: “Thank God! It feels as though my quest has reached its end. I will portray him,

undoubtedly. But... It’s as if I’ve seen the Infinite Sky. As if I’ve reached the shores of an Endless Ocean. How can I go on living in this world with such a ‘burden’?”

Can the infinity of the Sky and the Ocean, as seen by Abulkhayr, truly be depicted at all? What do the words “But...” and the ellipsis signify? Why does the novel include the anecdote about Sultan Husayn’s visit to Alisher’s grave? In our view, this legend is introduced to emphasize the delicate sensitivity required in literature. In Sultan Husayn’s recollections, there is a longing for childhood—a recognition of the grace of Dehlavī, the wonder of Lutfī, and the source of Navoi’s joy. He was a man of mood and feeling. He could sense spiritual states. The author wishes to see Abulkhayr in a state of renewed strength and vitality. For he believes the spirits of great ancestors hold a powerful, guiding force. Creating a character like Alisher Navoi has become a spiritual necessity for O. Muxtor. His consciousness, imagination, and perception are filled with awe and wonder, and he strives to transform these delicate, vibrant inclinations into a form that aligns with his nature and talent, thereby more fully expressing his essence. Navoi’s personality, having transcended conventional molds and not fitting within the confines of the four classical sciences, leads to emotions in the author’s heart that differ from formal viewpoints. The unique expression, tone, feeling, and interplay of colors, along with the epic narrative style of the author-narrator’s figure, and the vividness of character, stand out.

In general, the novel addresses the logic of creation and existence. The author compares Navoi’s role in the life of the people and the country with the flourishing of a strong centralized state during the time of Ismail Samani and Amir Temur, noting the progress, development, prosperity, science, art, and culture that thrived, contrasting it with the later period of the shahs. O. Muxtor does not separate Navoi’s fate from that of Sultan Husayn. He views him as a trusted advisor to Sultan Husayn, a guarantor of peace in the country. The thirty-year period of relative peace during the crisis is not only attributed to Sultan Husayn’s abilities but also to Navoi’s influence, urging him toward righteous actions.

References:

1. Qo‘shjonov, M. “Ishq ahli” novel analysis // Sharq Yulduzi, 2001. First issue.
2. Pardayeva, Z. Badiiy-estetik tafakkur rivoji va o‘zbek romanchiligi. Tashkent: 2002.